

From Tour Guide Narratives to Destination Loyalty: The Role of Perceived Flow and Tourist Satisfaction

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Abstract

The emotional and cognitive processes experienced by visitors have become key determinants of destination competitiveness in tourism. In this context, tourist guides are not merely information providers but crucial actors who interpret and enrich the overall experience. The aim of this study is to examine the effects of tourist guide narration on perceived flow, tourist satisfaction, and destination loyalty within an integrated research model. The research was conducted with 492 domestic tourists who visited the Çanakkale Martyrs' Memorial and Battlefields in Çanakkale through guided tours. The findings indicate that guide narration enhances tourists' concentration and immersion, thereby strengthening the flow experience and significantly increasing tourist satisfaction. The study contributes to the literature by providing a holistic model that explains how guide narration shapes tourist experiences and behavioral outcomes.

Key words: Tour Guide Interpretation, Perceived Flow, Tourist Satisfaction, Destination Loyalty

JEL Code: L83, M31, Z32

1. Introduction

Tour guides are key actors who shape tourists' experiences within a destination and facilitate the completion of their visits in the most effective way. As one of the most critical components of the tourism industry, tour guiding represents a comprehensive and highly valuable profession. Tour guides simultaneously appeal to tourists' multiple senses, enabling them to experience the cultural, historical, and social fabric of a destination. They allow visitors to visualize past events, understand local lifestyles, taste traditional foods

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and feel a sense of belonging to the place. Moreover, by conveying myths, art, legends, and historical narratives, guides enrich tourists' overall experiences (Ulusoy & Avcıkurt, 2019).

One of the primary roles of tour guides is their interpretive function, which determines how information is presented to visitors. Rather than simply transmitting facts, guides tailor their narratives according to different tourist profiles. This approach not only enhances tourists' perceived flow but also increases satisfaction, improves knowledge acquisition, and enables tourists to derive maximum value from their experiences (Aktaş & Koroğlu, 2021). Consequently, tourists' attachment to the destination may also be strengthened.

High-quality guiding services not only enable tourists to gain deeper insights into the destinations they visit but also help them better understand cultural and historical richness. In this process, guides' communication skills and professional attitudes play a critical role in meeting tourist expectations. Qualified guides can increase tourist satisfaction and positively influence destination image. Even tourists who initially hold negative perceptions about a destination may revise their views through high-quality guiding services, developing more favorable attitudes. This demonstrates how guiding services shape tourists' perceptions and satisfaction levels.

This study aims to examine the effects of tour guide narration on perceived flow, tourist satisfaction, and destination loyalty. A review of the literature indicates that tour guiding has been examined through dimensions such as performance, storytelling ability, and cultural interpretation, and these factors have been shown to influence tourist satisfaction and loyalty (Huang et al., 2015; Alazaizeh et al., 2022; Shi & Ann, 2023; Lin et al., 2024; Aytakin et al., 2025). Some studies conceptualize guiding services not merely as information transfer but as experiential processes involving value co-creation (Leong et al., 2024), while others focus on outcomes such as trust and purchasing behavior (Chang, 2014). In particular, previous research has demonstrated how guide narration influences tourists' psychological processes through variables such as flow experience and playfulness (Kuo et al., 2016).

Building upon this literature, the present study extends these theoretical frameworks to the context of the Çanakkale Martyrs' Memorial and Battlefields, which hold a unique symbolic and emotional significance in Türkiye's collective memory. Using a relatively large sample of 492 domestic tourists, this study distinguishes itself by testing a comprehensive model that explains how guide narration contributes to destination loyalty through perceived flow and tourist satisfaction, thereby addressing an important gap in the national literature.

2. Literature Review

Tour Guide Narration

Tour guides are professionals who possess expertise in a specific language and are capable of effectively conveying destination-related information while transforming the travel experience into a memorable one (Ap & Wong, 2001). For both individual tourists and package tour groups, guides are often the individuals with whom tourists interact most during their trips (Değirmencioğlu, 2001). Therefore, the ability of guides to deliver narratives that align with the characteristics of the destination and the concept of the tour directly affects the quality of tourists' experiences.

Tour guides are responsible for creating a destination image and ensuring the success of tour operations through the provision of high-quality services (Zhang & Chow, 2004). By transforming what might otherwise be perceived as ordinary or insignificant places into meaningful and engaging experiences through effective storytelling, guides play a critical role in the success of the tourism industry (Tosun & Temizkan, 2004).

An effective guide should be able to capture the attention of the tour group by developing strong narration skills and communicating clearly and fluently in front of an audience. This requires not only technical skills such as breath control, diction, and emphasis (Güzel, 2007), but also competencies in behavioral psychology and effective communication (Weiler & Black, 2015).

Kim et al. (2010) emphasize that effective guide narration should be tailored to the demographic characteristics and travel experiences of tourists. Information delivery should be objective, avoiding excessive personal interpretation, while maintaining both educational and artistic qualities. In addition, the narrative should be engaging and stimulating, encouraging tourists to explore the destination more deeply. Thus, guides are expected not only to inform but also to inspire.

Tour guiding is a dynamic profession shaped by individual skills, education, and experience. Although the tourism sector includes various service types such as accommodation, the performance of tour guides remains one of the most critical determinants of service quality (Prakash & Chowdhary, 2010). According to Huang, Hsu, and Chan (2010), the quality of guiding services is directly dependent on individual guide performance, highlighting the importance of developing a unique narration style.

Furthermore, Lugosi and Bray (2008) argue that service quality in tourism directly influences customer satisfaction, and tour guides constitute an integral part of this process. Similarly, Koçoğlu and Kalem (2023) demonstrate that guides' abilities in information delivery, narration, and interaction significantly affect tourist satisfaction.

Tour guides are key actors who enrich tourist experiences by effectively conveying historical and cultural values. To achieve this, they must possess strong storytelling and descriptive skills, as well as a genuine interest in the destination. Their interpretive abilities help tourists understand the historical and cultural depth of the places they visit (Alderson & Low, 1985). Miguel (2012) further highlights that guides act as cultural mediators, and their interpretive skills are decisive in enhancing tourist satisfaction. Therefore, tour guides should adopt an approach that goes beyond information transmission and focuses on delivering meaningful and engaging travel experiences.

Perceived Flow

Perceived flow refers to a psychological state in which individuals are fully immersed in an activity, experiencing deep concentration and enjoyment. In such a state, individuals lose their sense of time and place while deriving high levels of pleasure from the activity (Davras & Şahinkaya, 2024).

The emotions experienced during flow are not determined solely by the objective characteristics of the activity but are closely related to individuals' subjective perceptions of the balance between task difficulty and their own skills (Decloe et al., 2009). In tourism contexts, flow has been recognized as an important factor that enhances self-confidence and encourages repeat participation in similar activities (Tsaour et al., 2013).

The concept of perceived flow has gained increasing attention in tourism literature (Meng & Xu, 2010), and numerous studies have examined its role (Kuo et al., 2016; Kim & Park, 2017; Sthapit & Coudounaris, 2018; Kim & Thapa, 2018; Zhang et al., 2021). However, due to its multifaceted nature and varying interpretations across studies, flow remains a complex construct that is difficult to operationalize (Frochot, 2019). Therefore, further research is needed to better understand its implications (Abuhamdeh, 2020; DeMatos et al., 2021).

Tourist Satisfaction

Similar to other service sectors, the tourism industry operates within a highly competitive global environment and seeks to provide unique experiences. In this context, tourist satisfaction is of critical importance for stakeholders. In the literature, tourist satisfaction has been defined in various ways but is generally considered a psychological state resulting from tourists' evaluations of their experiences and interactions with different service components within a destination (Qiu et al., 2026).

Baker and Crompton (2000) define tourist satisfaction as the emotional state experienced after completing a travel experience, whereas Chen and Tsai (2007) conceptualize it as the outcome of the extent to which tourism experiences meet tourists' expectations, desires, and needs.

Tourist satisfaction is closely related to destination choice and loyalty (Koçoğlu & Yıldırım Kalem, 2023). Satisfied tourists are more likely to share their positive experiences with others and to revisit or reuse the same tourism services (Carvache-Franco et al., 2025). Therefore, satisfaction is considered a key antecedent of loyalty (Çatı & Koçoğlu, 2008).

Destination Loyalty

Destination loyalty refers to tourists' long-term commitment to a destination based on accumulated experiences and knowledge (Martin et al., 2013). Understanding how destination loyalty can be developed, maintained, and enhanced is essential in tourism marketing (Flavián et al., 2001).

The literature identifies destination loyalty as a core concept, with numerous studies examining its determinants (Alazaizeh et al., 2022). Research indicates that when tourists are satisfied with the services provided at a destination, they are more likely to revisit and recommend it to others (Huang et al., 2015; Marques et al., 2021).

Strong emotional attachment, repeated visitation, and positive word-of-mouth recommendations are crucial for destinations (Koçoğlu, 2019). In this process, tour guides act as a bridge between tourists and destinations by meeting tourists' informational and experiential needs, thereby enhancing revisit intentions (Reisinger & Steiner, 2006).

3. Methodology

Relationships Between Variables and Hypotheses

When studies examining the effect of tour guide narration on perceived flow are reviewed, Myllykangas and Gosselink (2002) found that the interpretive skills of tour guides increase satisfaction within the flow experience, while Cooper (2009) stated that tour guides can play an important role in enabling tourists to experience flow. The quality of the information provided by guides, the way it is presented, and the level of interaction significantly affect tourists' ability to focus on the activity and enjoy the experience. Therefore, a good guide can help tourists experience a more intense flow state. Meng and

Xu (2010) concluded that when a customer enters a state of flow through the quality of interpretive services, they filter external information and achieve deep concentration on a particular product or service. Wu and Liang (2011) emphasized that tour guide interpretation is associated with perceived flow, where individuals become fully absorbed in an activity, and this intense concentration provides them with a pleasant and valuable experience. Similarly, Kuo et al. (2016) found that tour guide interpretation has an effect on the flow experience. Based on this information, Hypothesis H1 was developed.

H₁: Tour guide narration has a positive effect on perceived flow.

In studies investigating the effects of tour guide narration on tourist satisfaction, it has been proven that effective tour guide narration has a positive impact on tourists' satisfaction. In his study on travel and tour organization, Mancini (2001) concluded that tour guides' interpretations also have an effect on travel quality and tourist loyalty. Huang et al. (2010) found that the interpretive abilities of tour guides have a significant and positive effect on the satisfaction of tourists who use guiding services. In addition, they concluded that the performance of guides indirectly affects tourists' satisfaction with tour services and their overall experiences. Likewise, studies conducted by Alazaizeh et al. (2022) and Lin et al. (2024) revealed that tour guides have strong communication with tourists and play an important role in ensuring tourist satisfaction. Based on this information, Hypothesis H2 was developed.

H₂: Tour guide narration has a positive effect on tourist satisfaction.

When studies examining the effects of tour guide narration on destination loyalty are reviewed, tourists' appreciation of the tour guide's interpretation leads them to leave the destination satisfied and, as a result, become loyal to that destination. Şahin (2012) found that the communication competence of tour guides creates a positive effect in their relationships with tourists. This relationship indicates that the effective communication skills of guides have the potential to increase tourists' loyalty to the destination. Studies conducted by Lee et al. (2011) and Chang and Kuo (2014) revealed that interpretation affects travel quality and tourists' destination loyalty. Chen et al. (2011) and Hall et al. (2011) concluded that positive tourist satisfaction increases the intention to revisit, repurchase, and recommend the destination to others. Kuo et al. (2016) identified the positive effects of tour guide interpretation performance on destination loyalty. Similarly, studies by Cheng et al. (2019), Shi, Ma and Ann (2023), and Lin, Zhang and Yhang (2024) found that the quality of tour guide interpretation positively affects destination loyalty. Based on this information, Hypothesis H3 was developed.

H₃: Tour guide narration has a positive effect on destination loyalty.

In studies examining the effects of perceived flow on tourist satisfaction, the flow theory proposed by Csikszentmihalyi and LeFevre (1989) suggests that when individuals are fully concentrated on an activity, they feel more active, alert, focused, happy, satisfied, and creative. As a result of their empirical analyses, they found that in both work and leisure contexts, individuals experience greater satisfaction when they are engaged in immersive environments. Myllykangas and Gosselink (2002) also found that the flow experience leads individuals to feel satisfied. Csikszentmihalyi (2003) stated that flow experiences contribute to emotional balance, increase productivity, and promote feelings of enthusiasm and satisfaction. Similarly, studies by Wu and Liang (2011) and Wang et al. (2022) reported that tourists' flow experiences increase positive emotions and satisfaction. Based on this information, Hypothesis H4 was developed.

H₄: Perceived flow has a positive effect on tourist satisfaction.

In studies examining the effects of perceived flow on destination loyalty, Novak et al. (2000) found that the flow experience attracts consumers and subsequently positively influences their attitudes and behaviors. Wu and Liang (2011), in their study on tourists, found that a positive flow experience increases tourist satisfaction, which in turn positively affects destination loyalty. Kuo et al. (2016), in their study on battlefield tourism in Taiwan's Kinmen region, concluded that perceived flow not only has a direct effect on destination loyalty but can also influence destination loyalty through tourist satisfaction. In other words, when tourists experience flow, this experience can directly increase their attachment to the destination, while also strengthening their loyalty through its effect on satisfaction. Tourists who experience more intense flow states during their destination experiences are expected to have higher levels of destination loyalty. Çeşmeci and Koçak (2020), who approached flow experience from the perspective of environmental experiences, also empirically confirmed the effect of flow on destination loyalty in the context of walking experiences. Although this relationship has not been widely examined in real environment contexts in the literature, another study testing this relationship exists. Kim and Thapa (2018), in their study on tourists participating in ecological package tours, similarly found that flow has a positive effect on destination loyalty. In this way, perceived flow emerges as an important factor that deepens tourists' relationship with the destination. Based on this information, Hypothesis H5 was developed.

H₅: Perceived flow has a positive effect on destination loyalty.

In studies examining the effects of tourist satisfaction on destination loyalty, Kozak and Rimmington (2000) stated that destination loyalty is one of the important factors affecting tourists' future purchasing decisions regarding travel products and services. This loyalty can be indirectly influenced by tour guides' interpretation performance through tourist satisfaction. Wu and Liang (2011) found that the satisfaction reported by tourists participating in rafting activities significantly increases their loyalty to the destination. This study shows that satisfaction directly affects tourists' tendency to recommend a destination. Lee et al. (2011), in a study conducted on Chinese tourists traveling to Korea, revealed that the quality of tour groups positively affects tourist satisfaction and that there is a positive relationship between satisfaction and destination loyalty. These results indicate that the quality of tour groups improves tourists' travel experiences and strengthens their attachment to the destination. Kuo et al. (2016), in their study on battlefield tourism in Taiwan's Kinmen region, examined the effects of tour guide interpretation performance and tourist satisfaction on destination loyalty. Their findings confirm that tourist satisfaction directly increases destination loyalty. Koçoğlu and Çatı (2008) also found that when tourists' expectations are met, satisfaction is achieved, and this satisfaction facilitates tourists' positive attitudes toward the destination, resulting in a strong relationship between satisfaction and destination loyalty. Based on this information, Hypothesis H6 was developed.

H₆: Tourist satisfaction has a positive effect on destination loyalty.

Research Method

When the relevant literature is examined, although there are a limited number of domestic studies examining the effects of tour guide narration on tourist satisfaction and destination loyalty, it is evaluated that there is no study on the relationship of perceived flow with these variables.

In this study, the effects of the narration skills of tour guides, who are among the important stakeholders of the tourism sector and who communicate directly with tourists,

on tourists' flow experience, satisfaction, and destination loyalty are examined. In this direction, the survey technique was used as a quantitative method.

Preparation of the Data Collection Tool

In the study, first, the "Tour Guide Narration" scale taken from Regnier, Gross and Zimmerman (1992) was used. The scale consists of a total of 19 items and 4 dimensions. The "Tour Guide Performance Scale," developed by Huang, Hsu and Chan (2010) based on the literature (Geva and Goldman, 1991; Mossberg, 1995; Wang and Fesenmaier, 2000; Ap and Wong, 2001; Zhang and Chow, 2004), was also used. This scale consists of a total of 36 items and 10 dimensions. Secondly, the "Perceived Flow Scale," consisting of 3 statements and taken from Novak, Hoffman and Duhachek (2003), was used in the study. Thirdly, the "Tourist Satisfaction Scale," consisting of 4 statements and taken from Ryu, Han and Kim (2008), was used. Finally, data were collected using the "Destination Loyalty Scale," consisting of 4 items and taken from Yoon and Uysal (2005), in order to determine tourists' destination loyalty levels. A 5-point Likert-type scale was used in the questionnaire form (1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree).

In order to ensure the language validity and content validity of the questionnaire, the format and content of the original scales in a foreign language were first examined before being translated into Turkish, and a preliminary evaluation was conducted to determine whether there were any linguistic or cultural barriers. The standard translation-back translation method proposed by Brislin (1986) was used in the translation of the scales.

Population and Sample

The study was conducted on 492 domestic tourists who visited the Çanakkale Martyrs' Memorial and Battlefields through guided tours. The research was carried out between January 2024 and May 2024, and the questionnaires were distributed to domestic tourists at the end of the tour through field guides and tour guides operating in Çanakkale. Since it was not possible to reach the entire population, the convenience sampling method was preferred in the study. As the population exceeds one hundred thousand, the sample size was determined using the formula for infinite populations commonly used in quantitative studies: "For $N > 10,000$ ($n = \sigma^2 \times Z^2\alpha / H^2$)" (Ural and Kılıç, 2013). As a result of the calculation, it is considered that 492 domestic tourists will provide good results in representing the population.

Research Model

Within the scope of the research model, a model was developed to examine the effects of tour guide narration on perceived flow (Meng and Xu, 2010; Wu and Liang, 2011; Kuo et al., 2016), tourist satisfaction (Huang et al., 2010; Wang et al., 2021; Alazaizeh et al., 2022; Lin et al., 2024), and destination loyalty (Cheng et al., 2019; Shi, Ma and Ann, 2023; Lin, Zhang and Yhang, 2024); the effects of perceived flow on tourist satisfaction (Wu and Liang, 2011; Wang et al., 2022) and destination loyalty (Kuo et al., 2016; Kim and Thapa, 2018; Çeşmeci and Koçak, 2020); and finally, the effect of tourist satisfaction on destination loyalty (Lee et al., 2011; Wu and Liang, 2011).

Fig. 1: Research Model

Source: Authors' calculations

4. Findings

Demographic Findings

According to the results of the frequency analysis, the demographic profile of the domestic tourists participating in the study is balanced but concentrated in certain groups. Slightly more than half of the participants consist of males (55.7%) and married individuals (51.7%). The age distribution is mainly concentrated between 25–44 years. While the education levels mostly consist of high school and associate degree graduates, the proportion of undergraduate and graduate degree holders is relatively low. In terms of income level, the largest group consists of middle-income participants, and the high-income group also represents a significant share.

Results of the Exploratory Factor Analysis for Tour Guide Narration

An exploratory factor analysis was conducted in order to determine the dimensions of the scale used to evaluate tour guide narration and to reveal the reliability and validity of this scale.

Factor analysis was applied separately to the scales of tour guide narration, perceived flow, tourist satisfaction, and destination loyalty in the questionnaire, and the factor structures of each scale were examined. The principal components analysis method was used for factor analysis, and the varimax orthogonal rotation method was preferred as the rotation technique. In order to evaluate the suitability of the data for factor analysis, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test was applied, and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was used to determine whether the variables were related to each other. Table 1 presents the results of the factor analysis conducted for the tour guide narration scale.

Table 1: Exploratory Factor Analysis for Tour Guide Narration

Factors	Factor Loadings	Variance %	C.Alpha
Fluent Interpretation			
The duration of the guide's narration was appropriate.	,919	23,827	,970
The guide demonstrated passion and interest through narration.	,909		
The guide's narration was monotonous and boring.*	,908		
The guide had studied and practiced before the narration.	,897		
The guide narrated fluently.	,886		
Guide Communication			
The guide communicated well with tourists.	,917	19,109	,958
The guide's narration made me feel comfortable and pleasant.	,912		
Through the guide's narration, I can now relate to the subject.	,931		
Thanks to the guide's narration, I have better knowledge about the battlefield.	,891		
Effective Narration			
The guide provided a comfortable narration environment.	,885	17,975	,948
The guide helped us understand local information.	,882		
The guide provided different narration content for different visitors.	,860		
The content of the guide's narration about the historical site was rich.	,847		
Experience Satisfaction			
The guide's narration was vivid.	,901	14,546	,942
I gained information from the guide's interpretations.	,900		
The guide's narration was pleasant.	,891		
Emotional Narration			
The guide's narration excited me about this historical site.	,871	13,196	,926
The guide's narration was clear and understandable.	,850		
The guide's narration was interesting.	,753		
Total Variance: 88,653			
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis			
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization			
Number of Iterations: 6			
KMO Sampling Adequacy: ,754			
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity: $\chi^2 = 12318,148$ p = 0,000			

Source: Authors' calculations

According to Table 1, as a result of the factor analysis conducted on the tour guide narration scale, it was observed that the scale was grouped under five different factors. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) sampling adequacy was calculated as 0.754. According to the literature, it is stated that at least 300 samples are generally required for the applicability of factor analysis (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2019). Accordingly, the obtained value is suitable for the analysis. According to the results of Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity, the obtained chi-square statistic (Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity χ^2 : 12318.148, $p = 0.000 < 0.01$) was found to be significant, and these findings indicate that the dataset comes from a multivariate normal distribution and has sufficient data for factor analysis (Hair et al., 1998).

According to the results of the exploratory factor analysis, the statements in the scale were grouped according to different narration and interpretation domains: The first factor includes 5 items related to the guide’s fluent interpretation. The second factor includes 4 items measuring the guide’s communication, and the third factor includes 4 items related to effective narration. The fourth factor includes 3 items measuring experience satisfaction, and finally, the fifth factor includes 3 items measuring the guide’s emotional narration. These factors demonstrate the effectiveness of the tour guide narration. As a result of the analyses, it is understood that each factor measures a specific interaction and emotion, and that the structural composition of the scale is detailed in this way.

When the Cronbach’s Alpha values calculated for each factor are examined, it was determined that the first factor, Fluent Interpretation, has a value of 0.970; the second factor, Guide Communication, 0.958; the third factor, Effective Narration, 0.948; the fourth factor, Experience Satisfaction, 0.942; and the fifth factor, Emotional Narration, 0.926. These values are the Cronbach’s Alpha coefficients indicating the internal consistency of each factor. Cronbach’s Alpha is a statistical measure used to evaluate the internal consistency of a scale and indicates how reliable each factor is in measurement. According to Nunnally and Bernstein (1994), if the Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient is 0.70 or higher, the internal reliability of the scale is considered acceptable.

Results of the Exploratory Factor Analysis for Perceived Flow

The factor analysis conducted on the perceived flow scale in the questionnaire was carried out to examine the internal structural properties of the scale. In this analysis, the principal components analysis method was used. In order to evaluate the suitability of the data for factor analysis, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) sampling adequacy measure and Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity were applied to determine the existence of relationships among variables. Table 2 presents the results of the factor analysis conducted for the perceived flow scale.

Table 2: Exploratory Factor Analysis for the Perceived Flow Scale

Factors	Factor Loading	Variance %	C.Alpha	α
Perceived Flow				
I felt truly fascinated during this tour.	,981			
I did not realize how time passed during this tour.	,968			
I did not feel anything during this tour.*	,930	92,139	,957	
Total Variance: 92,139				
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis				
KMO Sampling Adequacy: ,712				
Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity: $\chi^2 = 1895.126$ $p = 0,000$				

Source: Authors' calculations

In the examination of Table 2, the factor analysis conducted for the three items determined the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) sampling adequacy as 0.712. The findings are sufficient for factor analysis. According to the results of Bartlett's Test of Sphericity, the obtained chi-square value was found to be statistically significant (Bartlett's Test of Sphericity χ^2 : 1895.126, $p = 0.000$). Bartlett's Test of Sphericity is a test used to evaluate the suitability of the data for factor analysis. If the p-value obtained as a result of Bartlett's Test of Sphericity is less than 0.05, this indicates that the data are suitable for factor analysis (Hair et al., 1998).

Results of the Exploratory Factor Analysis for the Tourist Satisfaction Scale

Factor analysis was applied to the tourist satisfaction scale in the questionnaire, and principal component analysis was used in this analysis. In order to evaluate the suitability of the data for factor analysis, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) sampling adequacy measure and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity were used to test the existence of relationships among variables. Table 3 details the results of the factor analysis conducted for the tourist satisfaction scale.

Table 3: Exploratory Factor Analysis for the Tourist Satisfaction Scale

Factors	Factor Loading	Variance %	C.Alpha α
Tourist Satisfaction			
I felt pleasant emotions during the tour.	,897		
I am satisfied with having taken this tour.	,885		
I really liked this tour.	,820		
I was satisfied with the overall atmosphere of this tour.	,802	72,597	,869
Total Variance: 72,597			
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis			
KMO Sampling Adequacy: ,670			
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity: $\chi^2 = 1158.812$ $p = 0,000$			

Source: Authors' calculations

When Table 3 is examined, the findings related to the factor analysis are summarized. As a result of the analysis, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) sampling adequacy for the four items was found to be 0.670. When the KMO value is between 0.60 and 0.70, the sampling adequacy is considered "adequate" (Kaiser, Henry, 1974, p.31). According to the results of Bartlett's Test of Sphericity, the obtained chi-square value was found to be significant (Bartlett's Test of Sphericity χ^2 : 1158.812 $p = 0.000$). This result indicates that the items in the dataset are sufficiently related to each other and form a structure suitable for factor analysis.

Results of the Exploratory Factor Analysis for the Destination Loyalty Scale

Factor analysis was applied to the destination loyalty scale included in the questionnaire, and the factor structure of the scale was examined. In this analysis, the

principal component analysis method was used. Table 4 presents the results of the factor analysis conducted for the destination loyalty scale.

Table 4: Exploratory Factor Analysis for the Destination Loyalty Scale

Factors	Factor Loading	Variance %	C.Alpha	α
Destination Loyalty				
I will revisit the Çanakkale Battlefields.	,937			
I will revisit the Çanakkale Martyrs' Memorial and Battlefields.	,928			
I will revisit the Çanakkale Martyrs' Memorial and Battlefields.	,873	79,551		,910
I will recommend this tour to others.	,826			
Total Variance: 79,551				
Extraction Method: Principal Component				
Analysis KMO Sampling Adequacy: ,737				
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity: $\chi^2 = 2091.495$ p = 0,000				

Source: Authors' calculations

According to the data presented in Table 4, the analysis shows that the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) sampling adequacy for the four items is 0.737. In factor analysis, it has been stated that when the factor loadings of four or more items or variables are 0.60 or higher, reliable results can be obtained regardless of the sample size (Hair et al., 1998). According to the results of Bartlett's Test of Sphericity, the obtained chi-square value was found to be statistically significant (Bartlett's Test of Sphericity χ^2 : 2091.495 p = 0.000).

Mean and Standard Deviation Findings for the Variables

Table 5 presents the mean and standard deviation values of the participants regarding tour guide narration, perceived flow, tourist satisfaction, and destination loyalty.

Table 5: Mean and Standard Deviation Values of the Variables

	Mean	Standard Deviation
Tourist Satisfaction	4,26	0,61
Destination Loyalty	4,16	0,68
Guide Communication	4,13	0,98419
Fluent Interpretation	3,96	1,08
Effective Narration	3,96	0,96555
Emotional Narration	3,86	0,98809
Experience Satisfaction	3,84	1,04
Perceived Flow	3,55	1,38

Source: Authors' calculations

When Table 5 is examined, it is observed that among the sub-dimensions of Tour Guide Narration, Guide Communication has the highest mean value with 4.13. This is followed by Fluent Interpretation with a mean of 3.96, Effective Narration with a mean of 3.96, Emotional Narration with a mean of 3.86, and Experience Satisfaction with a mean of 3.84. The mean of Perceived Flow was found to be 3.55, the mean of Tourist Satisfaction

was found to be 4.26, and the mean of Destination Loyalty was found to be 4.16. These findings indicate that tourists appear to be quite satisfied with guide services and their experiences, and that guides' communication skills and narration styles contribute to tourists' satisfaction levels. However, since the perceived flow factor may have more variable values among tourists, it suggests that tourist experiences may differ depending on individual perceptions.

Findings Related to the Testing of Research Hypotheses

Regression analysis is a statistical method used to determine the relationship between one dependent variable and one or more independent variables. This analysis method enables modeling and predicting the effect of independent variables on the dependent variable. Regression analysis is used to find a linear or nonlinear model that best represents the data points (Hair et al., 1998, p. 155). In Table 12, the regression analysis conducted to test Hypothesis H₁ regarding the relationship between tour guide narration and perceived flow is presented. This table statistically shows how tour guide narration affects the overall perceived flow level of tourists.

Table 6: Findings Related to the Simple Regression Analysis Between Tour Guide Narration and Perceived Flow

Research Model (Dependent Variable: Perceived Flow)			
Independent Variable	Beta	t	P
Tour Guide Narration	,150	3,356	,000
R=,150; R ² =,023; Adjusted R ² =,023; F=11,265; p= 0.000			

Source: Authors' calculations

According to the results of the simple linear regression analysis in Table 6, the model used was found to be statistically significant ($F = 11,265.19$; $p < 0.05$). This finding indicates that the independent variable in the analysis is successful in explaining the change in the dependent variable. The value of 0.150 given as the beta coefficient measures the effect of tour guide narration on perceived flow. This coefficient shows that as tour guide narration increases, perceived flow also increases in a similar manner. In other words, when tourists perceive the guide's narration as more effective and engaging, their flow experiences can be said to be more fluent and coherent. When the t-statistic ($t = 3.356$) and the p-value ($p < 0.05$) are examined, the effect of tour guide narration on perceived flow is found to be statistically significant. These findings can be interpreted as indicating that guide narration is a real factor affecting the flow experience and not a random relationship. According to the results of the linear regression analysis, a positive relationship was found between the variables; $R = 0.150$. The independent variable, tour guide narration, significantly explains the dependent variable, perceived flow; the R² value was calculated as 0.023. These findings suggest that tour guide narration can increase tourists' flow experience.

Results of the Multiple Regression Analysis on the Effect of Tour Guide Narration and Perceived Flow on Tourist Satisfaction

The multiple regression analysis conducted to evaluate the effect of tour guide narration and perceived flow on tourist satisfaction was used to test the H₂ and H₄ hypotheses of the study. According to the analysis results presented in Table 7;

Table 7: Findings of the Multiple Regression Analysis on the Effect of Tour Guide Narration and Perceived Flow on Satisfaction

Research Model (Dependent Variable: Tourist Satisfaction) – Multicollinearity Statistics					
Independent Variables	Beta	t	P	Tolerans	VIF
Tour Guide Narration	,430	10,662	,000	,977	1,023
Perceived Flow	,155	3,846	,000	,977	1,023
R=,478; R ² =,229; Adjusted R ² =,225; D-W=1,905; F=72,027; p= 0.000					

Source: Authors' calculations

It shows that Tour Guide Narration (Beta = 0.430, t = 10.662, p < 0.001) and Perceived Flow (Beta = 0.155, t = 3.846, p < 0.01) have a positive and statistically significant effect on tourist satisfaction. The tolerance values for both independent variables were calculated to be high (0.977) and the VIF values were low (1.023). When VIF values are below 10, it is accepted that there is no multicollinearity problem among the variables. This indicates that the independent variables can be safely used together in the model (Field, 2000).

There is a positive relationship between the variables (R = 0.478). The R² value, which represents the explanatory power of the independent variables on the dependent variable, was calculated as 0.225. In the analysis, the Durbin–Watson statistic was also examined and found to be (D-W = 1.905). This statistic was used to evaluate the possibility of autocorrelation. Among the methods used to determine whether there is autocorrelation in the error terms is the Durbin–Watson test. These tests evaluate whether the error terms in the regression model are related to each other. If the result of these tests is between 1.5 and 2.5, the Durbin–Watson (D-W) value indicates that there is no autocorrelation (Kalaycı, 2006, p. 264). The tolerance value should also not be less than 0.200. These criteria are important measures used to evaluate the validity and reliability of the model in regression analyses. The F statistic (F = 72.027, p = 0.000) indicates that the independent variables used together significantly explain the dependent variable and that the model is generally significant. This multiple regression analysis shows that Tour Guide Narration and Perceived Flow variables have a positive and statistically significant effect on tourist satisfaction. In addition, it is observed that the model has a good overall fit and that the explanatory power of the independent variables on the dependent variable is high.

Results of the Multiple Regression Analysis on the Effect of Tour Guide Narration, Perceived Flow, Tourist Satisfaction, and Destination Loyalty

The multiple regression analysis conducted to evaluate the effects of tour guide narration, perceived flow, and tourist satisfaction on destination loyalty was used to test the H₃, H₅, and H₆ hypotheses of the study. The analysis results presented in Table 8 show these relationships.

Table 8: Findings of the Multiple Regression Analysis on the Effect of Tour Guide Narration, Perceived Flow, Tourist Satisfaction, and Destination Loyalty

Research Model (Dependent Variable: Destination Loyalty) – Multicollinearity Statistics					
Independent Variables	Beta	t	P	Tolerans	VIF
Tour Guide Narration	,097	2,896	,004	,792	1,262

Perceived Flow	,005	0,169	,886	,949	1,054
Tourist Satisfaction	,704	20,726	,000	,771	1,296

R=,754; R² =,569; Adjusted R² =,566; D-W=1,919; F=212,011; p= 0.000

Source: Authors' calculations

According to the results of the multiple regression analysis, the beta coefficient obtained for tour guide narration as an independent variable is 0.097. This value indicates the effect of tour guide narration on destination loyalty. As a result of the t-test, it was found to be ($t = 2.896$ and $p = 0.004$). This shows that tour guide narration has a statistically significant effect on destination loyalty. The tolerance value was calculated as 0.792 and the VIF value as 1.262, indicating that there is low multicollinearity between tour guide narration and the other independent variables. For the independent variable of perceived flow, the beta coefficient obtained is 0.005. As a result of the t-test, it was found to be ($t = 0.169$ and $p = 0.886$), and these findings indicate that perceived flow does not have a statistically significant effect on destination loyalty. The tolerance value was calculated as 0.949 and the VIF value as 1.054, suggesting low multicollinearity between perceived flow and the other independent variables. The beta coefficient obtained for the independent variable of tourist satisfaction is 0.704. As a result of the t-test, it was found to be ($t = 20.726$ and $p = 0.000$), indicating that tourist satisfaction has a strong and statistically significant effect on destination loyalty. The tolerance value was calculated as 0.771 and the VIF value as 1.296, therefore indicating low multicollinearity between tourist satisfaction and the other independent variables. The overall explanatory power of the multiple regression analysis was measured by the R value ($R = 0.754$). The R² value was calculated as 0.569, meaning that the independent variables used explain 56.9% of the variance in destination loyalty. The adjusted R² value is 0.566, which may indicate that the model has been purified from the effects of unnecessary variables. Finally, the Durbin–Watson statistic was calculated as 1.919, the F statistic as 212.011, and the p-value as 0.000, indicating that the probability of autocorrelation is low, and it was concluded from the F statistic that the model is statistically significant overall. According to the results of the multiple regression analysis, it was concluded that tour guide narration and tourist satisfaction positively affect destination loyalty, whereas perceived flow does not play a statistically significant role on destination loyalty. The hypothesis results are presented as a whole in Table 9.

Table 9: Hypothesis Results

Hypothesis Results			Standar d Values	Standar d Errors	t- value	p- value	Result
H₁	Tour Guide Narration	→ Perceived Flow	,150	,089	3,356	,000	Accepted
H₂	Tour Guide Narration	→ Tourist Satisfaction	,430	,035	10,66 2	,000	Accepted
H₃	Tour Guide Narration	→ Destination Loyalty	0,97	,033	2,896	,004	Accepted
H₄	Perceived Flow	→ Tourist Satisfaction	,155	,015	3,846	,000	Accepted
H₅	Perceived Flow	→ Destination Loyalty	,005	,015	0,169	,886	Rejected
H₆	Tourist Satisfaction	→ Destination Loyalty	,704	,038	20,72 6	,000	Accepted

Source: Authors' calculations

When Table 9 is examined, it is determined that tour guide narration has a positive and significant effect on perceived flow (H_1 , $\beta = 0.150$, $p = 0.000$). The t-value and p-value indicate that this effect is statistically significant and that tour guide narration increases perceived flow. Therefore, the relevant hypothesis is accepted. The second hypothesis of the study, which states that tour guide narration has an effect on tourist satisfaction, is strong and positive (H_2 , $\beta = 0.430$, $p = 0.000$). The relatively high beta coefficient and the very low p-value indicate that the relationship is reliable, and it is observed that the hypothesis is accepted. Another hypothesis in the study, which states that tour guide narration has a positive effect on destination loyalty (H_3 , $\beta = 0.097$, $p = 0.000$), shows that the t-value and p-value are significant and that tour guide narration increases destination loyalty. It is also determined that the relevant hypothesis is accepted.

When Table 15 is examined, it is seen that perceived flow has a positive and significant effect on tourist satisfaction (H_4 , $\beta = 0.155$, $p = 0.000$), and the significance of the t and p values supports that this effect is statistically valid and that perceived flow increases tourist satisfaction. When the hypothesis (H_5 , $\beta = 0.005$, $p = 0.886$) is examined, it is found that perceived flow does not have a significant effect on destination loyalty. Since the p-value is relatively high and the t-value is low, it does not indicate a significant relationship, leading to the rejection of the hypothesis. Finally, the strong and significant effect of tourist satisfaction on destination loyalty (H_6 , $\beta = 0.704$, $p = 0.000$) shows that tourist satisfaction significantly affects destination loyalty. Therefore, the relevant hypothesis is also accepted.

5. Conclusions

Tour guides are known to play an important role in the tourism experience. Guides are considered tourism ambassadors who not only provide information about the destination but also shape tourists' experiences. In particular, the narration skills of guides have a determining effect on tourists' perceived flow experience, satisfaction levels, and their loyalty to the destination. This study aims to examine the effects of tour guide narration on perceived flow, tourist satisfaction, and destination loyalty at the Çanakkale Martyrs' Memorial and Battlefields.

Within the scope of the study, a questionnaire form was prepared to measure the effects of tour guide narration and perceived flow on the formation of satisfaction and destination loyalty of domestic tourists visiting Çanakkale. In line with the stated objective, the researchers took an active role in the direct implementation of the questionnaires. This situation is an important factor that increases the reliability of the study. The main objective of the research is to analyze in depth the effects of tour guide narration on perceived flow, tourist satisfaction, and destination loyalty.

In line with the hypotheses developed in this study, the relationships between tour guide narration, perceived flow, tourist satisfaction, and destination loyalty were tested, and the findings showed that the hypotheses were largely supported. Accordingly, it is seen that tour guide narration positively affects perceived flow, tourist satisfaction, and destination loyalty. Chang (2014) also found in his study that well-structured and engaging narration by guides contributes deeply to tourists' flow experiences. Similarly, Wong and Kwong (2004) examined the effects of guides' narration styles on tourists' satisfaction and flow experiences and identified a positive relationship. Andereck and Nyaupane (2011)

conducted a study showing that the quality of guide narration and the ability to provide detailed information increase tourists' flow experience. It has also been supported by similar studies (Huang et al., 2015; Shi et al., 2023; Leong et al., 2024) that effective, immersive, and interactive narration by the guide enables tourists to focus more on the experience and to engage more deeply in the process mentally.

On the other hand, another important result is that perceived flow positively affects tourist satisfaction. Perceived flow creates cognitive and emotional stimulation by enabling the tourist to actively participate in the experience, allowing the tourist to perceive this experience as unique and valuable. Indeed, this result is also confirmed by studies in the literature (Kuo et al., 2016; Li et al., 2024; Lin et al., 2024). However, our research findings reveal that the experience alone is not sufficient to increase destination loyalty. This situation shows that the effect of flow on destination loyalty may depend on additional factors such as satisfaction and other variables. Andereck and Nyaupane (2011) suggested that tourists' flow experiences increase their overall satisfaction and may contribute to destination loyalty. However, the results of our study indicate that the flow experience may not be sufficient to increase destination loyalty, even though it provides a satisfying experience. This finding reveals that the strong bonds that tourists establish with the destination and their overall satisfaction may outweigh the effect of the flow experience. In other words, the deep and strong connections that tourists establish with the destination and their high levels of satisfaction may have a greater impact than the flow experience. Koçoğlu (2019) similarly examined the effects of perceived customer value on customer satisfaction and behavioral intentions and stated that customer satisfaction plays an important role, but may not be sufficient on its own. Finally, the hypothesis that tourist satisfaction positively affects destination loyalty was strongly confirmed, and it was revealed that satisfaction is one of the most important determinants of loyalty.

In light of the findings obtained within the scope of the research, efforts to increase perceived flow are of critical importance in increasing product differentiation and maintaining competitiveness. The fact that different types of tourists have different expectations requires tour guides to adjust their interpretations according to characteristics such as age, gender, and education level of tourists. For example, it has been determined that the majority of tourists visiting the Çanakkale battlefields are between the ages of 25–34. In this case, tour guides can make their narration more modern, engaging, and original. In this context, organizing storytelling workshops for tour guides and enriching narration techniques with visual and auditory materials will strengthen their creative narration methods and ensure destination loyalty. Seeking support from local sources and cultural consultants for destination knowledge, analyzing post-tour feedback, and making necessary improvements will play a critical role in increasing tourist satisfaction and destination loyalty. These concrete steps will support the professional development of guides while improving tourist experiences and perceived flow, thereby strengthening destination loyalty.

For future research in the field of tourism, studies can be conducted with different samples to better understand the effects of guide narration and perceived flow on tourist satisfaction and destination loyalty in light of these findings. In addition, large-scale studies examining the effects of flow on destination loyalty through the mediating role of tourist satisfaction will help to better understand the indirect effects of flow. Furthermore, multidisciplinary studies investigating the effects of psychological and social factors on flow, satisfaction, and loyalty will provide more comprehensive results. In this way, it will be possible to develop a more comprehensive and in-depth understanding of tour guides' narration skills and their effects.

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